

ACUTE PER ORAL TOXICITY OF TILMICOSIN – SUBSTANCE "BIOVET" AD IN WHITE RATS (FISCHER – 344)

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ABSTRACT

The acute oral toxicity of Tilmicosin – a substance "Biovet" in rats, was studied. 42 male white rats, Fischer 344 line, weighing 160–180 g, were treated with 10% aqueous solution of Tilmicosin phosphate Biovet using a gastric tube. For each dose (500, 1000, 1500, 2000, 2500, 3000 and 3500 mg/body weight), 6 were treated once. Rats, which were monitored for 7 days, taking into account the clinical picture of their intoxication and mortality.

Based on the Litchfield-Wilcoxon method used in the test, an average lethal dose of LD₅₀ 2200 (2860 ± 1692) mg/body weight ($p = 0.05$) and relatively lethal doses of LD₁₆ = 1142 and LD₈₄ = 3256 mg/body weight were determined, which classify the product as low toxic.

The results regarding the acute toxicity of Tilmicosin when administered orally to white rats confirm the studies conducted with the original Eli Lilly product that Tilmicosin has low toxicity when administered for oral use – LD₅₀ > 2000 mg / body weight (Piroozi, K.S. et al. 1993).

Key words: tilmicosin, acute per oral toxicity, rats.

Introduction

Tilmicosin is a semi-synthetic, macrolide antibiotic that has been used in the United States since 1992 (3), derived from tylosin–20–Deoxy–20 – (3,5–dimethyl piperidin – 1–41) – desmycosin (82–88% cis isomer and 12–18% trans isomer). It exhibits an antimicrobial spectrum similar to tylosin, but its effect is more pronounced against *Pasteurella haemolitika* and *Pasteurella multocida*, causes of pneumonia in cattle and sheep, and with respect to *Actinobacillus pleuropneumoniae* and *Pasteurella multocida*, causative agents of pneumonia. also against mastitis agents in sheep – *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Mycoplasma agalactiae*.

Tilmicosin is used to treat respiratory diseases in cattle, but a number of authors have argued that it can be used in horses, pigs, sheep, goats, rabbits and turkeys (Jordan F.T. et al. 1999, Mateusen B., et al. 2001, McKay S.G et al. 1996, Ramadan, A. 1997, Wakambayachi, K. and Yamada. S. 1972).

Phosphate salt (Tilmicosin phosphate) is used in the preparation of medicinal products. It is only administered orally (pigs, rabbits, chickens) or subcutaneously (cattle, calves, sheep over 15 kg), never intramuscularly and intravenously. It metabolizes slowly in the body (the usual s.c. dosage is a single dose – 10 mg / body weight).

In pigs, it is administered in the form of a premix added to the feed at a dosage of 200 to 400 ppm. The following pharmaceutical forms have been developed on the basis of Tilmicosin 'Biovet': Tilmovet 30% (solution for injection), Tilmovet 20% (premix for medicated feed), Tilmovet 20% (granules for oral administration) and Tilmovet 25% (oral solution).

The purpose of this study was to determine the LD₅₀ of Tilmicosin, a „Biovet“ substance, after single, oral administration in white rats.

LD₈₄ = 3256 mg/body weight, which defined the product as low toxic. Pathologically, no visible changes in the internal organs were observed, either in the dead experimental animals or in the euthanized rats at the end of the experiment.

According to the Hodge-Sterner classification as well as the Melnikov classification, (Melnikov, N. N. 1987) Tilmicosin refers to the group of slightly toxic substances. According to the literature data, LD₅₀ for Tilmicosin when administered orally to white rats (Sprague Dawley) after a fasting diet is 850 mg/body weight (Anonimus. 1999, Christodouloupoulos G. 2002, Jordan, W.H, et al. 1993, Jordan F. T., et al. 1999).

In experiments with no prior fasting diet, LD₅₀ was > 2000 mg/body weight (Piroozi, K. S., 1993, Roberts, G.1999). Our results regarding the acute toxicity of Tilmicosin when given to oral rats in white rats confirm the studies conducted with the original product of Eli Lilly (USA) according to which Tilmicosin has low LD₅₀ toxicity > 2000 mg/body weight when administered internally (Piroozi, K. S., et al. 1993).

Table 1: Acute toxicity studies of Tilmicosin – a ‘Biovvet’ substance in male white rats.

Doses mg/body weight	Observed effect Num. of Experi- enced / Num. of dead	Observed effect		Expected effect		Difference be- tween observed and expected ef- fect%	Collectable on X 2
		to break through	%	to break through	%		
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
500	0/6	2.67	1.0	3.10	2.9	1.9	0.0130
1500	1/6	4.03	16.7	4.17	20.3	3.6	0.0310
2000	3/6	5.00	50.0	4.88	45.3	4.7	0.0100
2500	4/6	5.43	66.6	5.51	69.5	2.9	0.0045
3000	5/6	5.97	83.3	5.91	81.8	1.5	0.0015
3500	6/6	6.90	97.1	6.35	91.1	6.0	0.0046

Table 2: Reported signs of intoxication in experimental animals in the individual groups.

The dose mg/body weight	Hour/day	SIGNS OF INTOXICATION					
		Reduced mo- tor activity	Sleepiness	Difficulty breathing	Ataxia	Coma	Died
500	Time 1–12	3/6	6/6	0/6	0/6	0/6	0/6
	Time 12–24	3/6	4/6	0/6	0/6	0/6	0/6
	Day 2	0/6	0/6	0/6	0/6	0/6	0/6
	Day 7	0/6	0/6	0/6	0/6	0/6	0/6
1500	Time 1–12	5/6	5/6	2/6	0/6	1/6	1/6
	Time 12–24	3/5	2/5	1/5	0/5	0/5	0/5
	Day 2	0/5	0/5	0/5	0/5	0/5	0/5
	Day 7	0/5	0/5	0/5	0/5	0/5	0/5
2000	Time 1–12	4/6	4/6	3/6	4/6	2/6	2/6
	Time 12–24	3/4	2/4	2/4	1/4	1/4	1/4
	Day 2	0/3	0/3	0/3	0/3	0/3	0/3
	Day 7	0/3	0/3	0/3	0/3	0/3	0/3
2500	Time 1–12	6/6	6/6	4/6	3/6	2/6	2/6
	Time 12–24	2/4	2/4	1/4	1/4	2/4	2/4
	Day 2	0/2	0/2	0/2	0/2	0/2	0/2
	Day 7	0/2	0/2	0/2	0/2	0/2	0/2
3000	Time 1–12	5/6	6/6	5/6	3/6	3/6	3/6
	Time 12–24	3/3	3/3	3/3	1/3	2/3	2/3
	Day 2	1/1	1/1	1/1	1/1	0/1	0/1
	Day 7	0/1	0/1	0/1	0/1	0/1	0/1
3500	Time 1–12	6/6	6/6	6/6	2/6	4/6	4/6
	Time 12–24	2/2	2/2	2/2	2/2	2/2	2/2
	Day 2	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0
	Day 7	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0

Macrolide antibiotics rarely show side effects. Some of them have been reported to cause cardiovascular effects or impaired renal function at doses above the therapeutic dose (McKay S.G. et al. 1996). High-dose tilmicosin, outside the subcutaneous route of administration in some animal species, also leads to cardiovascular toxicity (Christodouloupoulos G, et al. 2002). It causes a positive chronotropic and a negative inotropic effect, a weakening of cardiac activity and increased breathing, which was also observed in our experiments. According to some authors, the cardiovascular effect of Tilmicosin is not associated with lipid peroxidation of the heart (Modric, S. et al. 1998). Some researchers have used the creatine kinase enzyme as biochemical criteria for cardiotoxicity (Gheith, A. et al. 2015, Womble A. et al. 2006, Yazar, E. et al. 2004). Gastrointestinal malaise, vomiting, lifting, and damage to the liver may occur frequently after administration of macrolide antibiotics (Bureau Report. 1995). Tilmicosin has been shown to have a different side effect compared to other macrolidic – cardiotoxicity, depending on the animal type, route of administration and dose (Christodouloupoulos G, et al. 2002, Jordan, W. H, et al. 1993, Jordan F. T. et al. 1999, McKay S. G., et al. 1996).

Tilmicosin at a dose of 15 mg/body weight has been shown to be safe and effective in young lambs with respiratory infections (Christodouloupoulos G, et al. 2002). It has been shown that it can cause transient swelling at the injection site, acute dyspnoea, anaphylaxis, collapse and death, and these manifestations have specific relationships (Barragry, T. B. 1994, Bureau Report. 1995, Georgiev, B. et al. 2010, Jordan, W. H, et al. 1993). Some researchers claim that tilmicosin toxicity is due to positive chronotropic and negative inotropic cardiovascular effects (Christodouloupoulos G, et al. 2002, Jordan F. T. et al. 1999).

Our attempts to determine the acute toxicity of Tilmicosin "Biovet" show that the oral preparation of white rats is low toxic and does not lead to side effects. Its administration in the form of medicated feed for pigs in the prophylactically therapeutic dose (200 to 400 ppm) does not pose any toxicological risks.

Conclusion

The mean lethal dose (LD₅₀) of Tilmicosin – a Biovet substance administered once daily after 12 h fasting diet in male white rats (Fischer – 344) was 2200 (2860 ÷ 1692) mg/body weight at p = 0.05, LD₁₆ = 1142 and LD₈₄ = 3256 mg/body weight.

According to the Hodge-Sternier scale Hodge-Sternier Tilmicosin – a substance can be classified as low toxic.

The clinical picture of intoxication is characterized with decreased movement activity, drowsiness, difficulty breathing, ataxia and coma.

At the necropsy of both the dead and the euthanized surviving experimental animals have not been shown any visible changes in the internal organs.

References

1. Georgiev, B., Vangelov, S., Kostadin, L., Bankova, R., Hristoskova, E., Arnaudova, E. (2010). *Veterinary Pharmacological Handbook*. Sofia
2. Melnikov, N. N. (1987). *Pesticides*. Moscow "Chemistry", 20–21.
3. Anonimus. (1999). *Tilmicosin. Committee for Veterinary Medicinal Products*. Summary Report (1).
4. Barragry, T. B. (1994). *Aminoglycosides, macrolides, and lincosamides*. In: *Veterinary Drug Therapy*, 241–263, Williams & Wilkins, Philadelphia, USA.

5. Bureau Report. (1995). *Suspected drug adverse reactions reported to The Bureau of Veterinary Drugs*. Can. Vet. J., 36, 246–49.
6. Christodoulopoulos G, Warnick L. D, Papaioannou N, Fthenakis, G. C. (2002). *Tilmicosin administration to young lambs with respiratory infection: Safety and efficacy considerations*. J Vet Pharmacol Ther, 25:393–397.
7. Gheith, A. El-Mahmoudy, A. Elmajdoub & S. Awidat. (2015). *Pharmacovigilance of Tilmicosin in Mice*. Acta Scientiae Veterinariae. 43: 1318.
8. Jordan, W. H, R. A. Byrd, R. L Cochrance, G. K. Hanasomo, J. A. Hoyt, B. W. Mainq, R. D. Meyerhoff, R. D. Sarazan. (1993). *A review of the toxicology of the antibiotic Micotil 300*. Veterinary and Human Toxicology, 35, 151–158.
9. Jordan F. T., Forrester C. A., Hodge A. and Reeve-John-Son L.G. (1999). *The comparison of an aqueous preparation of tilmicosin with tylosin in the treatment of Mycoplasma gallisepticum infection of turkey poults*. Avian Dis., 43, 521–525.
10. Kart A, Yapar K, Karapehlivan M, Citil M. (2007). *The possible protective effect of L-carnitine on tilmicosin-induced cardiotoxicity in mice*. J Vet Med a Physiol Pathol Clin Med, 54:144–146.
11. Litchfield Y. Y., F. Wilcoxon. (1949). *Asimplified method of evaluating dose – effective experiment*. J. Pharm. Exp. Therap., 96, 99–113.
12. Mateusen B., Maes D., Hoflack G., Verdonck M. & De Kruif A. (2001). *A comparative study of the preventive use of tilmicosin phosphate (Pulmotil premix[®]) and Mycoplasma hyopneumoniae vaccination in a pig herd with chronic respiratory disease*. Journal of Veterinary Medicine, Series B. 48(10): 733–741.
13. McGuigan, M. A. (1994). *Human exposures to tilmicosin*. Vet. Hum. Toxicol, 36, 306–308.
14. McKay S. G., Morck D. W., Merrill J. K., Olson M. E., Chan S. C. and Pap K. M. (1996). *Use of tilmicosin for treatment of pasteurellosis in rabbits*. Am. J. Vet. Res., 57, 1180–1184.
15. Modric, S., A. I. Webb, H. Derendorf. (1998). *Pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of tilmicosin in sheep and cattle*. J. Vet. Pharmacol. Therap, 21, 444–452.
16. Piroozi, K. S., Keaton, M. J., & Jordan, W. H. (1993). *The acute toxicity of tilmicosin administered orally to Fischer 344 rats*. Unpublished study No. R21493 from Lilly Research Laboratories. Submitted to WHO by Lilly, Basingstoke, UK.
17. Ramadan, A. (1997). *Pharmacokinetics of tilmicosin in serum and milk of goats*. Res. Vet. Sci., 62, 48–50.
18. Roberts, G. (1999). *Inchem. 878 Tilmicosin*. WHO Food Additives Series 38, 1–16.
19. Wakabayachi, K., S. Yamada. (1972). *Effect of several macrolide antibiotics of blood pressure of dog*. Japanes Journal of Pharmacology, 22, 799.
20. Womble A., Giguère S., Murthy Y., Cox C. & Obare E. (2006). *Pulmonary disposition of tilmicosin in foals and in vitro activity against Rhodococcus equi and other common equine bacterial pathogens*. Journal of veterinary pharmacology and therapeutics. 29 (6): 561–568.
21. Yazar, E., E. Ozterkin, A. Sivrikaya, R. Col, M. Elmas, A.L. Bas. (2004). *Effect of Different Doses of Tilmicosin on Malondialdehyde and Glutathione Concentrations in Mice*. Acta Vet. Brno, 73, 69–72.